

**MORE ABOUT THE FMG SYSTEM (FREE MOVEMENT OF GASES) KUZNETSOVA.
KUZNETSOV'S FMG SYSTEM.**

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Abstract

The text compares two fuel combustion systems - the Forced Draft Gas (FDG) system and the Free Movement of Gases (FMG) system. It explains the limitations of traditional FDG furnaces and boilers, where gases cannot separate by temperature in the combustion chamber, leading to inefficient and dirty combustion. The patented FMG system allows temperature separation of gases, enabling an oxidation-reduction reaction that increases efficiency 30%, eliminates CO₂ emissions, and allows countless clean heat generator configurations. The text urges adopting FMG standards, given FDG's pollution and climate impacts. It notes resistance to FMG adoption in the US, EU and Russia, citing corruption. But FMG's design aligns with nature's laws, and transition from FDG is straightforward. The text aims to inform consumers so they can choose between the two systems wisely.

Keywords: Forced Draft Gas (FDG) system, Free Movement of Gases (FMG) system, Oxidation-reduction reaction, Efficiency, Atmospheric pollution, Heat generators, Transition from FDG to FMG, Standards, CO₂ emissions, Clean fuel combustion, Climate crisis, Clean fuel combustion, Laws of nature

Before you choose a furnace, boiler, you need to know what fuel burning systems exist in the world. What are their capabilities.

The customer, who decides what kind of household furnace to build, needs to understand well the essence of the question. I want to detail the differences, opportunities, prospects, in the existing methods of fuel combustion.

Figure 1 - convection furnace systems

Figure 1 (A.E. Shkolnik) shows the furnaces of the FGM (Forced Gas Movement) system.

- A. Successive
- B. Parallel
- C. Buctless (capped)
- D. Combined
- E. Air chamber

1. Single-turn
2. Double-turn
3. Multiturn
4. Air chamber

In it, the movement of the gas flow occurs due to the draft of the pipe. The main feature of the FDG

(Forced Draft Gas) furnace is that the separation of gases by degree of heating does not occur in the firebox. The convection system includes gases mixed with ballast gases. For this reason, the I.S. Podgorodnikov and V.E. Furnaces of the Grum-Grjimalo system, FDG furnaces and not a two-tier hood, but a single-tier hood.

In the firebox during combustion there are combustion products, hot CO₂, H₂O. There are also combustible gases - products of incomplete combustion. In case of lack of air, they are able to burn and form explosive mixtures with air, carbon monoxide, soot and various hydrocarbons. All come out into the pipe, worsening the ecology. With excess air, the combustion temperature decreases (the efficiency decreases). At

different stages of fuel combustion, it is difficult to accurately supply the required amount of air for combustion to the firebox. Therefore, over the firing cycle, incomplete combustion products and excess air come out into the pipe. Both are bad. In US standards, the first and last 5 minutes of results are not taken into account. This is wrong, self-reassurance. When the damper is closed at the wrong time, the furnace cools down quickly. The gas flow moves up, down, left, right. The heating of the furnace is uneven. There is no place in the furnace to accommodate a heat exchanger. In the firebox, the heat exchanger reduces the combustion temperature, that is, the efficiency. The length of the channel for the release of gases reduces the draft of the pipe and the temperature of the outgoing gases, which causes condensation, water enters the pipe and destroys it. It is impossible to create multifunctional furnaces, including high power ones. Each furnace, boiler and heat generator must be certified. MAINLY, it is impossible to create conditions for the redox reaction to proceed in it. By the course of which the main issues on combating the climate crisis are solved by building a clean and fair energy economy and introducing innovations in the field of renewable energy sources.

FMG (Free Movement of Gases) System.

The French scientist A. Lavoisier, in 1777, created the oxygen theory of combustion. He described the redox combustion reaction. These are countercurrent parallel chemical reactions occurring simultaneously. However, no one could create conditions for its flow. I did it.

In Russia on March 5, 2014, I patented the Fuel Combustion Method, RU 2 553 748. The Ministry of Energy gave the name to the invention "FMG (Free Movement of Gases) Kuznetsov System". It creates conditions for such a reaction to flow, which corresponds to the laws of nature and practically solves the indicated problems. It is characterized by high efficiency, clean combustion, lack of CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere. The ability to create countless heat generators for various functional purposes and new technologies.

In the FMG system, the movement of gas flow particles occurs due to heat exchange processes. Hot particles move up, cooled ones down. It creates conditions for redox reactions.

A lot of air is supplied to the furnace. Oxygen enters the reaction in the required amount at each period of time. Excess air - ballast gases descend downwards and enter the pipe. It releases warm air (without water vapor) at a temperature below 100 degrees Celsius, possibly up to 40 degrees, and condensation does not occur in the pipe.

In the furnace, the separation of gases by degree of heating occurs. The hot combustion products CO₂ and H₂O enter through a dry seam into the upper part of the hood combined with the furnace. Having given off heat, they descend down along the walls. Hydrocarbon comes towards them. When carbon affects CO₂ and H₂O, a restoration reaction occurs. Flammable gases, 2CO and water gas arise, THIS IS ADDITIONAL FUEL. When secondary air is supplied, they are oxidized (burned, products arise, hot gases CO₂ and H₂O) rise up the hood. The oxidation-reduction process occurs simultaneously. This continues as long as combustion occurs in the furnace. Additional fuel arises and burns. Efficiency increases. The movement of gas flows occurs due to heat exchange processes.

To test FMG system furnaces, a new standard must be developed and approved. In the FDG system, efficiency and purity are measured by gases from the pipe.

From the FMG system pipe comes only warm air. According to the standard, it is necessary to measure the heat transfer from the surface of the furnace. The furnace is marked with squares.

A sensor is placed in each square. Measurements are taken every 5 seconds from the initial temperature to the final temperature equal to the initial one.

For example, the initial temperature is 20 degrees, then the measurements stop at the same temperature. Then it will be possible to determine the amount of heat and heat emission time.

Unlike the FDG system, for FMG system heat generators, only the furnace needs to be certified. All furnaces of any power are made according to this standard, only of a different size, larger or smaller, respectively, depending on the furnace power.

Using the FMG system for combustion, it is possible to eliminate the disadvantages in the manufactured FDG system heat generators.

For example, in water-tube and gas-tube boilers:

In the diagram, the scheme of a water-tube boiler: 1 - fuel supply, 2 - furnace, 3 - pipes for water movement; the direction of its movement is indicated by the numbers 5, 6 and 7, the place of water inlet - 13, the place of water outlet - 11 and the drain point - 12, 4 - the zone where the water begins to turn into steam, 19 - the zone where there is both steam and water, 18 - steam zone, 8 - partitions that direct water movement, 9 - flue and 10 - chimney, 14 - steam outlet through the separator 15, 16 - outer surface of the water tank (drum).

What are the disadvantages here and how can they be eliminated:

The water in the drum is heated only from below and through the pipes passing through the furnace. The

bottom of the drum and the pipes are a cold core in the furnace and reduce the combustion temperature there;

The movement of gases in the furnace is forced, due to the draft of the pipe, that is, this is a FDG (Forced Draft Gas) system. In the furnace there is no separation of gases by degree of heating. The combustion reaction products, hot CO₂ and H₂O, ballast gases (air with an increased nitrogen content and carbon monoxide) are mixed, reduce the combustion temperature there and quickly leave the pipe. Inefficient and dirty combustion.

The same can be said about the gas-tube boiler.

Scheme of a gas-tube boiler:

1 - fuel and water supply, 2 - combustion chamber, 3 and 4 - convection tubes with hot gas exiting further through the flue (positions 13 and 14 - flue), 5 - grate between the tubes, 6 - water inlet, outlet indicated by

number 11 - its outlet, in addition at the outlet there is a device for measuring the amount of water (marked with number 12), 7 - steam outlet, steam formation zone marked with number 10, 8 - steam separator, 9 - outer surface of the container in which water circulates.

In the FMG system, the hood can be any size. A container for water (drum) of any size can be inserted into it so that its entire surface is heated, including above the steam. All the disadvantages of the above furnaces and boilers are eliminated. Not only water is heated, but also steam. Steam heating calculation must be done, we could not. In addition, there is the possibility of regulating the heating of the container. It needs to be patented.

In the USA, EU and Russia to the present time, outdated FDG system furnaces are being built. Furnace builders are being trained to build FDG system furnaces. People receive inefficient, dirty furnaces and boilers that pollute the atmosphere. These countries allocate huge funds to solve this problem. On May 22, 2015, the FUEL COMBUSTION METHOD, FMG Kuznetsov System was patented in Russia. (this name

is reflected in the documents of the MINISTRY OF ENERGY of RUSSIA). This is a significant step forward in solving many world problems. Practical tests of the invention were carried out with scientists from the Ural Federal University. The Ministry of Energy of Russia approved the method and recommended in a letter to contact development institutions to integrate the Fuel Combustion Method into the country's energy system. However, our proposals were not supported there. A loan at 10% was offered.

The Federal Service for Intellectual Property Patent and Trademark is to blame for this, as well as some corrupt federal officials. A corrupt federal team was created with the aim of re-registering the Patent to another person. Everything that has been developed over several decades is being destroyed. We are blocked

everywhere possible. Our team has been virtually destroyed. This continues to this day. The METHOD could have been integrated into Russian and global energy 10-15 years ago.

The hood can be any shape and volume. Various heat exchangers can be inserted into it. The hood can have multiple furnaces. The furnace can have multiple hoods. This makes it possible to regulate the temperature of heat exchangers located in different places both horizontally and vertically. This makes it possible to create a countless number of heat generators for various functional purposes and capacities. CO₂ and H₂O do not come out into the pipe, but are restored to combustible gases and burned. Warm air comes out of the pipe. The result is clean and efficient combustion.

The transition from the FDG system to the FMG system is simple, from small to large, from simple to complex. The website <http://www.stove.ru/> has free drawings of many FMG system furnaces. They are about 30% more efficient than FDG system furnaces.

People from many countries use the drawings, including the USA, Germany, Sweden, Canada, where these furnaces have been tested for efficiency. There is an article "To help people making our furnaces."

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